

USE OF MARKETING PRINCIPLES IN THE MANAGEMENT ACTIVITIES OF THE ENTERPRISE IN THE CONDITIONS OF MODERNIZATION OF THE ECONOMY

Kholbekov Rafiqjon Alimbekovich

Independent researcher of Tashkent State University of Economics

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7228416>

Abstract: In the article, ensuring the innovative attractiveness of industrial complex enterprises in the implementation of the state innovation policy, methods of using marketing principles in the management activities of the enterprise in the conditions of economic modernization, the innovative attractiveness of enterprises, objective aspects that serve to effectively allocate funds to innovative projects, the export and scientific and technical potential of enterprises, the level of financial stability, the level of diversification of production, the quality of innovative programs, etc. were analyzed.

Key words: Enterprise, marketing, economy, modernization, innovation, attractiveness, project, finance, stability.

In the implementation of the state innovation policy, it is important to ensure the innovative attractiveness of the enterprises of the industrial complex. Currently, the state of 387 innovation in the real sector of the economy cannot be said to be satisfactory. Many industrial enterprises are not competitive, their fixed assets are morally and physically old. In such conditions, the innovative policy of the state, aimed at the development of industrial production and increasing the innovative attractiveness of individual economic entities, plays an important role. In our opinion, the innovative attractiveness of the enterprises of the industrial complex is a set of objective aspects that serve to effectively allocate funds to innovative projects. It is determined by the export and scientific and technical potential of enterprises, the level of financial stability, the level of diversification of production, the quality of innovative programs, etc. Ensuring the innovative attractiveness of the enterprises of the industrial complex is an important direction of the efficiency of the national economy. We believe that it is necessary to develop a comprehensive government program for its implementation. Comprehensive evaluation of the innovative potential of industrial enterprises and improvement of the quality of internal factors affecting innovative activity should serve as the main directions of this program. As part of the measures used to increase the innovative attractiveness of the enterprises of the industrial complex, it is necessary to provide for the development of high-tech, demanding sectors such as aircraft construction, rocket-space production, atomic industry, biotechnology. It serves as a basis for

technical-technological rearmament of the national economy and improvement of production efficiency. The innovative attractiveness of the subjects of the industrial complex depends on the support of enterprises and organizations by the state. This can be done in the following ways: the establishment of centralized financial investments on the basis of payment and repayment; implementation of real innovative projects and financing of innovative projects based on selection; promoting the expansion of the practice of joint financing of innovative projects by state and commercial organizations. In this case, it is necessary to pay great attention to the development of the market of innovative projects taking into account their quality expertise, high efficiency and reimbursement. Liquidation of low-efficiency and loss-making enterprises, financial rehabilitation of the industrial sector due to their re-specialization is an important result of state activity. A very necessary step for this is the restructuring of the industrial complex. On the basis of the above proposals, it is possible to create the necessary conditions for the development of innovative projects for the purpose of mastering modern technologies, production of competitive products, creation of advanced programs of goods and services, which are considered a clear factor in strengthening the material base of the economy of Uzbekistan. Thus, a new 388 system of state support for the development of science was formed in Uzbekistan. It is aimed at ensuring the concentration of forces and means aimed at solving the most necessary issues of sustainable economic development. To ensure sustainable economic growth, it is necessary to conduct an active innovative, industrial, structural, scientific and technical policy. This, in turn, serves as a basis for the entire society for the beginning of the restoration of the state's economic power. In the scientific research carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the issues of interdependence and interaction between innovations and enterprises and the financial and economic conditions of the entire economy have not been fully studied in the necessary volume and in a systematic way. The necessity of this analysis goes back to the relations such as the implementation of economic reforms related to the financial support of the ongoing structural restructuring in the republic. Innovative activity affected all sections of the society and became a systematic flow of the development of economic processes. A systematic approach is to consider the evolution and implementation of innovation processes as an interdependent whole. It helps to identify the mechanisms that serve as the basis for the multifaceted connections between the financial status of industrial enterprises and innovations, which characterize the economic potential of the society. An important determining factor of the state of the

economic potential of the state is the activity of the enterprises of the real sector of the economy with various branches. The efficiency of the production sector is also characterized by the size and contribution of labor resources employed in production, the contribution and size of production funds employed in various sectors of the economy, value and natural indicators of the volume of production, and financial indicators.

It is known that innovations are necessary for the implementation of expanded reproduction, for the acceleration of scientific and technical progress, for increasing the quality and competitiveness of national production, for the structural reconstruction of social production and the development of all sectors of the national economy, for the creation of the necessary raw material base for industry, and the problem of unemployment. solution, as well as serving as a basis for solving many other problems 389. All these together help to improve the economy of the country. The state of innovative activity in the country can be characterized by the dynamics of the indicators of the connection between innovations and the economy: - the total volume of innovative products; - the contribution of the innovative product to the volume of the produced product in general; - number of innovative active enterprises, etc. In recent years, the rate of development of the innovative sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan does not correspond to modern trends, despite the positive change in the indicators of innovative activity. This is explained, first of all, by the fact that our republic is moving to market relations where the market of scientific and technical goods is not yet fully formed. On the one hand, this is the weakness of the resource base necessary for innovative development and the insufficient financial basis, the setting of high rates for taxes and budget and non-budget fees. At the same time, it is necessary to emphasize that the solution of the legal and regulatory framework for innovative entrepreneurship is incomplete, and there is no general status of innovative entrepreneurship subjects. On the other hand, it is the inability of innovative enterprises and organizations to quickly adapt to changes in the external environment, the decline or abandonment of structural restructuring in innovative enterprises, the reduction of qualified scientific and management personnel in enterprises, the lack of strategic management culture and business planning. can be shown. The objective reason for this situation is that the development of innovative entrepreneurship and the problems of innovation management have not been studied methodologically. In addition, the decrease in the innovative activity of enterprises to a certain extent characterizes the insufficient efficiency of innovation. When researching innovative processes, it is necessary to take into account the following main

principles: - competition between manufacturers claiming to receive state subsidies; - financing of enterprises that achieve "synergistic effect". In this case, the result from all capital investments will be higher than the result from all its separate elements. This can be achieved by clearly directing resources to perform strictly defined tasks, accelerating the turnover of tools, as well as at the expense of innovative activities and the return of tools. Taking these principles into account, it is necessary to thoroughly evaluate innovative projects from the point of view of their economic efficiency. 390 As for government expenditure, they represent allocations to working capital that are part of the annual consumption cycle and help support their activities. Innovations and budget policy are interconnected and affect not only innovative activities, but also the state of the state economy and its level of development. The state of the state economy, the dynamics of its development is the main factor that determines the financial capabilities of the state in terms of ensuring the standard of living of the population. One of the main directions of interdependence of innovations and state economic development is through the implementation of scientific and technical policy. In this case, it is necessary to take into account the need to implement the targeted program of restructuring the industry, improving and developing the scientific and technical base of the national economy, increasing the productivity of social labor, and rationally using economic resources, while increasing the potential of highly qualified personnel of the industrial complex. Innovations are also necessary to achieve such goals as expansion and development of production, reduction of moral and physical wear and tear of fixed assets, increase of technical level of production, improvement of quality of products created by individual enterprises and ensuring their competitiveness. Ultimately, they are necessary to ensure the normal functioning of enterprises in the future, stable financial condition and maximum profit. The deepening of the interdependence of scientific and technical and economic development, the transformation of scientific and technical development into the main source of economic growth, in turn, has a great impact on the nature of the interaction between military and civilian technologies.

The role of the factor of secondary use of the achievements of scientific and technical progress is growing not only in the United States, but also in all the leading developed countries of the world. On the one hand, this is due to the increase in the dependence of the modern armament system on information technology, and on the other hand, it helps to increase the contribution to the creation of scientific and technical innovations and the introduction of new technological processes to increase the potential of the economy. Costs for

technological innovation are determined by the size of investments. Capital investments intended for the reconstruction of operating enterprises, the development of existing workshops and production, and the reconstruction of objects related to raising its technical and economic level based on the achievements of scientific and technical development are considered very close to it. More than half of all capital investments intended for production are spent on reconstruction and technical re-equipment of the enterprises operating today. The main factor creating a desire for innovation is the low level of profitability and competitiveness of goods in terms of scientific and technical indicators. Entrepreneurs who are among the first to introduce innovations 391 release high-quality products to the markets or produce goods with much less spending. Entrepreneurs who lag behind technical progress, produce outdated products or use old technology will lose their share in the market. Management of innovative activities is carried out within the framework of the state economic policy strategy, and the main means of management should be investment programs and projects aimed at the leading directions of the economic development of the state, its separate sectors and regions. Thus, it is of scientific and practical importance to analyze the nature and interdependence of the relationship between innovations and the country's economic development. Innovations are related to the economy, they affect the improvement of economic indicators, help to stabilize the economy and solve socio-economic problems. Innovation is one of the most important economic categories. In any country, innovative activity with an indicator below the established threshold and its further decline poses a serious threat to national security. It is for this reason that there is a need to scientifically substantiate the features of innovative activity in the conditions of reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The theoretical and practical importance of the analysis of the relationship between innovation and the country's economic situation is that it allows for the development of an active and effective innovation policy, the identification of factors affecting the effectiveness of innovation activity and innovation. World experience shows that the continuous implementation of innovations that ensure quality growth in all areas has become the driving force of society and economic development. Today, countries where innovative models of development and "smart" technologies are implemented are the most successful and stable. The sustainable development of such countries, their competitiveness in world markets is based not on the export of natural resources and the use of physical labor, but on innovative ideas and developments. In these countries, the implementation of the state strategy for

the introduction of innovative ideas, developments and technologies is conventionally carried out by special agencies known as "ministries of the future". The main task of the agencies responsible for innovative development is to ensure the country's economic growth and competitiveness in world markets, as well as the increase of the intellectual share in the economy, due to the wide introduction of innovation and scientific achievements. In 2017-2021, the action strategy for the five priority areas of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan has defined specific goals for the fundamental improvement of the population's well-being and quality of life, the comprehensive and rapid development of society and the state, the modernization of the country, and the liberalization of all spheres of life. In other words, we should turn Uzbekistan into a stable market economy with a high share of innovation and intellectual contribution in production, a modern and competitive industry in the global market, as well as a rapidly developing country with a favorable investment and business environment. It is impossible to achieve the set goals without fully transitioning Uzbekistan to the innovative model of development, which requires the creation of an effective system of state support for innovative activities in the country and the promotion of the practical implementation of innovative ideas, developments and technologies in public administration, priority sectors of the economy, and the social sphere. However, despite the rich intellectual and infrastructural potential, the implementation of innovations in the country is on a systematic basis.

In our opinion, the interrelationship of the economic situation of Uzbekistan with innovation can be seen in the following main aspects: - firstly, from the point of view of researching the impact of innovative activity on the national economy, seeing it as a whole as a material basis of the state; - secondly, when analyzing the impact of innovations on the activity of a particular enterprise, consider it as a separate market entity; - thirdly, to study the socio-economic consequences of the implementation of innovative policy. In our opinion, it is better to carry out this activity based on the functions performed by innovations.

Conclusion: One of the main means of influencing the country's economy and the business activities of economic entities is the innovative policy of the state economic policy. With the help of innovative policy, the state can directly influence the increase in the rate of production, the acceleration of scientific and technical progress, the change of the structure of social production, and the solution of social problems.

References:

1. Kasimova M.S., Akhmedov O.M., Yodgorov M.Kh., Marketing research. - T. Teacher, 1998.
2. Kasimova M.S., Ergashkhojaeva Sh.J. Marketing. Study manual.- T.: TDIU, 2004y.
3. Makhmudov H.E "Economics of Enterprise" Tashkent, Literature fund in 2004.
4. Theoretical and ideological sources of beruni's philosophical views //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary ..., 2020.
5. Central Asia V IX-XII : Social-political situation, spiritual-cultural development // Academicia Globe: international research. 2021/4/30 Tom.Nº4-S -148-151.
6. Vzgl'yad zapadnyx uchenyx na filosofiyu Avitsenny (Abu Ali ibn Sina) // - Nauchnyy zhurnal, 2019